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The rate of temperature change used in thermal limit studies has been shown to have significant effects on experimental outcomes¹.

Rate of change effects examined using Collembola

These widespread and abundant microarthropods form vital links between above and below-ground components of terrestrial ecosystems⁸, and are important in soil ecosystem functioning⁹. Most species breed well under optimal temperature and moisture conditions and have short generation times making Collembola a good model system for these studies.

Methods

Critical thermal maxima (CT_{max}) and minima (CT_{min}) determined by ramping temperature up/down from set point until coordinated movement can no longer be maintained. Desiccation and starvation effects were controlled for. Data were analyzed using a generalized linear model (normal distribution and identity link function) in STATISTICA v. 10.

Results

Mean CT_{max} (A) and mean CT_{min} (B) under three rates of temperature change for polar (blue) and temperate (red) Collembola species. Dashed lines indicate soil-dwelling species, solid lines indicate species that occur in surface litter. Vertical bars indicate mean ± 95% confidence interval, n = 25-30 for each species at each rate and sequential letters designate significant differences (P < 0.05) between rates for each species.

Fast rates of change appear to increase thermal tolerance overall, except for the CT_{min} of *H. viatica* (B), which is lowest at the slowest rate of change.

Conclusions

A general decline in CT_{max} was found despite controlling for potential desiccation and starvation effects, showing that these effects do not account for declining CT_{max} with declining rates of change. For CT_{min}, contrasting effects of rate among species were found, highlighting the species-specific nature of rate of change variation.

These preliminary results have implications for the assessment of these species' physiological safety margins under current climate change scenarios.